

byeo, seeding time had no effect on seeding establishment and for Gancheokbyeo and Gyehwabyeo, seeding establishment adversely affected them if they were seeded after June (Table 1).

Panicle number per unit area for Shinunbongbyeo was not significantly different for seeding time; for Gancheokbyeo and Gyehwabyeo, panicle number per unit area decreased if they were seeded after 10 Jun. For 1,000-grain weight, seeding time had no effect on all three varieties.

Spikelet number per unit area and percentage of ripened grains were reduced significantly when the seeding time was 10 Jun for all maturing types. Milled rice yield for Shinunbongbyeo was not affected by seeding time. For Gancheokbyeo and Gyehwabyeo, milling yield was reduced significantly

Table 2. Yield components and yield according to seeding times on wet field surface in reclaimed saline soil^a, Gyehwa, Korea, 1996-97.

Cultivar	Seeding time	Panicles (no. m ²)	Spikelets (no. m ²) × 10 ⁴	Ripened grain (%)	1,000-grain weight (g)	Milled rice yield (t ha ⁻¹)
Shinunbongbyeo	10 May	417 a	30.7 a	89 a	21.7 a	4.5 a
	20 May	414 a	30.6 a	89 a	21.4 a	4.4 a
	30 May	406 a	28.3 ab	87 ab	21.5 a	4.3 a
Gancheokbyeo	10 Jun	399 a	27.2 b	86 b	21.3 a	4.1 a
	10 May	411 a	31.6 a	90 a	22.7 a	4.5 a
	20 May	405 a	32.9 a	92 a	23.0 a	4.6 a
Gyehwabyeo	30 May	397 a	31.5 a	92 a	23.1 a	4.6 a
	10 Jun	361 b	25.3 b	86 b	22.2 a	3.8 b
	10 May	421 a	29.3 a	90 a	24.0 a	4.5 a
	20 May	412 a	31.0 a	90 a	24.3 a	4.8 a
	30 May	398 a	28.4 ab	87 b	23.9 a	4.4 b
	10 Jun	355 b	24.4 b	84 c	23.1 a	3.4 c

^aMeans followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by Duncan's multiple range test.

when the seeding time was late May and later (Table 2). The results indicated that the best seeding time for early-maturing types was from May to early

June. The most appropriate seeding time for mid- and late-maturing varieties was the middle of May. ■

Stress tolerance — excess water

Distinguishing seedling traits in deepwater rice (*Oryza sativa* L.)

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Deepwater rice genotypes are characterized by their elongation ability under excess water. This character is expressed approximately 4-6 wk after seeding. However, young germinating seedlings within 7-15 d after seeding can be identified for elongation ability from morphological characters such as mesocotyl elongation and length of the second leaf blade, which can be used to distinguish deepwater types from their nondeepwater counterparts.

A comparative assessment was made for these two parameters taking 10 genotypes from both deepwater and nondeepwater rice during the dry and wet seasons, 1996, at the Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack. Seeding was done at three depths—4, 6, and 8 cm—under normal pot culture as well as under dark with seeds germinated in petri dishes. Observations were recorded for mesocotyl elongation and length of the second leaf blade on 1-wk-

Length of mesocotyl and second leaf blade of deepwater and nondeepwater rice varieties (data pooled over two seasons).

Variety	Mesocotyl length (mm)			Germination in dark	Length of second leaf blade (mm)
	Seeding depth				
	4 cm	6 cm	8 cm		
Deepwater rice					
Jalamagna	26.15	37.10	53.40	3.75	37.40
TCA4	28.75	42.40	63.35	5.20	38.25
Jalanidhi	25.95	31.65	38.05	2.15	49.10
NDGR410	27.25	44.40	63.75	3.08	49.35
NDGR413	28.00	34.50	43.75	1.75	47.80
LPR85	27.05	36.75	50.80	2.25	47.10
TCA12	28.45	33.90	43.55	1.35	49.90
Chakia 59	26.55	38.00	43.25	1.60	48.10
Madhukar	26.55	34.50	46.05	1.87	48.15
Jalapriya	32.40	39.55	47.20	2.25	45.45
Mean	27.71	37.28	49.32	2.33	46.06
Nondeepwater rice					
Khao Y Khao	17.25	26.25	29.55	0.38	59.15
IET7590	21.85	28.15	36.15	0.40	59.90
Kwan-Fu-1	21.10	20.75	27.20	0.23	63.50
Mtu-6	22.10	28.75	38.35	0.58	56.45
TK Deep straw 34-774	17.55	26.20	27.40	0.10	50.60
Deep straw 24-500	12.40	19.35	21.20	0.05	58.95
Samson Polo (YS386)	21.45	25.05	37.85	0.55	54.25
Daeng Laem	17.85	18.85	22.90	0.45	62.65
Basmati 802	19.25	21.35	24.05	0.43	57.10
Savitri	13.25	15.80	19.90	0.28	51.00
Mean	18.41	23.05	28.46	0.34	57.36

old seedlings by taking a sample of 10 seedlings from each type.

The two seasons were found to be homogeneous, with nonsignificant differences for the two characters as tested

by Bartlett's test. The pooled data over two seasons (see table) indicated higher mesocotyl elongation for deepwater rice than for nondeepwater rice varieties for both pot culture and dark petri

dish culture. It was also evident that elongation was greater at higher seeding depths in all the test genotypes. On the contrary, the length of the second leaf blade as measured in seedlings raised under normal pot culture showed a reverse trend, i.e., the length was less for deepwater rice genotypes than for nondeepwater types.

These two seedling characters were used as morphological markers to evaluate germplasm and segregating lines for tolerance for deepwater conditions in our subsequent experiments. ■

Tolerance for submergence in rainfed lowland rice under repetition of flooding

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In South and Southeast Asia, rainfed lowland rice is generally affected by submergence during flash floods when the plant remains completely under water. The frequency and duration of floods differ from place to place and year to year, causing different degrees of plant mortality. Information on tolerance for single submergence is available, but it is lacking on cultivar survival because of recycling of flooding. These experiments were conducted to identify rice cultivars that could withstand different cycles of flooding.

The experiments were carried out during the wet season with 242 cultivars of the Assam Rice Collection (ARC), which is considered to be a rich source of germplasm because of its high degree of phenotypic divergence. The genotypes were direct-seeded with a spacing of 20 × 10 cm. Two seedlings hill⁻¹ were maintained by thinning after 10 d of germination. Twenty-day-old seedlings were submerged for 12 d under 60 cm of water followed by normal conditions with 10 cm of water. After 10 d from the removal of water pressure, that is, 42 d after sowing, a severe submergence treatment was

given to the regenerated seedlings for another 10 d under 80 cm of water. A survival count was taken visually immediately after drainage of the water, and was confirmed after 15 d.

Dissolved oxygen concentration was measured using a submersible polarographic oxygen electrode (Syland Model 610, Heppenheim, Germany). Light transmission was measured using a quantum underwater light sensor (Licor, Model 185B).

To determine yield and yield-contributing characters, an experiment was conducted under rainfed lowland conditions where water depth varied between 0 and 50 cm.

Light penetration inside the floodwater was comparatively less in second submergence than in first submergence, which suggested that the floodwater was more turbid during second submergence. Oxygen concentration

measured around 12 noon was above the air saturation (>7.36 ppm) level (Table 1), but susceptible checks were ruined because of the severe pressure of submergence (Table 2).

After second submergence, a few genotypes survived. Survival percentage was maximum in Matia (87%), followed by FR13A (85%), CR380-10 (60%), and ARC18112 (56%) and 18101 (51%). Sabita, a submergence-tolerant cultivar, identified earlier on the basis of single-submergence treatment, showed only 35% survival. After first submergence, when water receded, the elongated top leaves descended to the ground and ultimately decayed. Therefore, plant height just before second submergence was less than the height just after the completion of first submergence.

Yield and yield-contributing characters showed great variation

Table 1. Floodwater characteristics at around 12 noon. Data given as mean +SE.

Water depth (cm)	Days after first submergence			Days after second submergence		
	2	5	9	2	5	5
<i>Light transmission (%)</i>						
5	72.6 ± 0.4	70.4 ± 0.3	73.3 ± 1.2	68.4 ± 0.3	67.1 ± 0.6	62.2 ± 0.3
30	62.2 ± 0.6	64.5 ± 0.9	62.3 ± 1.0	56.0 ± 0.7	53.6 ± 1.1	45.9 ± 0.4
60	53.7 ± 0.5	53.6 ± 0.4	53.5 ± 1.0	50.1 ± 0.4	42.2 ± 1.1	37.6 ± 0.4
Mean	62.8	62.8	63.0	58.2	54.3	48.6
<i>Oxygen concentration (ppm)</i>						
5	7.37 ± 0.02	7.92 ± 0.14	7.40 ± 0.07	7.65 ± 0.04	7.82 ± 0.03	7.95 ± 0.05
30	7.47 ± 0.06	7.75 ± 0.13	7.57 ± 0.02	7.57 ± 0.01	7.77 ± 0.04	7.90 ± 0.05
60	7.92 ± 0.02	7.50 ± 0.12	7.55 ± 0.04	7.95 ± 0.03	7.90 ± 0.02	7.72 ± 0.05
Mean	7.59	7.72	7.51	7.72	7.83	7.86

Table 2. Survival percentage and changes in plant height because of repetition of flooding.

Germplasm/ cultivar	Seedling height (cm)				Survival (%) after second submergence
	First submergence		Second submergence		
	Before	After	Before	After	
FR13A	23	76	48	72	85
Sabita	29	97	44	74	35
CR380-10	34	100	53	98	60
Matia	35	107	61	100	87
ARC18112	27	91	34	86	56
ARC18101	28	90	41	85	51
ARC18104	28	87	36	83	46
ARC18172	32	91	41	81	42
ARC18198	29	83	42	80	40
Tulasi	25	70	34	52	03
Mahsuri	23	76	35	63	02
Mean	26	88	43	79	46